

Journal of EcoAgriTourism

Bulletin of Agri-ecology, Agri-food, Bioengineering and Agritourism

Vol. 19 (2023), No 2 (47)

Journal of EcoAgriTourism
ISSN: 1844-8577

Journal of EcoAgriTourism is a follow up, by translation in
English of "Revista de EcoAgroTurism"
ISSN 1841-642X, first issued in 2005

ISSN: 1844-8577

PRINCIPLES OF POLICY AND STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT FOR THE REALISATION FRAMEWORK MODEL OF THE INTEGRATED MOUNTAIN DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: In the context of the current challenges, it is well known that mountain areas are highly exposed and have serious problems to solve, which makes work on integrated mountain development timely. In this sense, the paper aims to deepen the conceptual understanding of the problem by applying some necessary principles (in particular the Mountain Convergence Principle) and by laying the foundations for the implementation of public policies and strategies in order to develop a framework model of integrated mountain development applied in the Romanian mountain area for the next decades. The high impact development directions, such as gastronomy and mountain tourism, as well as the integration based on the multifaceted factors and action in engineering, management and cultural-spiritual areas specific to mountain and foothill areas are highlighted. The study describes a framework model of integrated mountain development, addressing a series of structural and functional aspects at a systemic level, with theoretical and practical applications for the evolution of mountain areas.

Keywords: development, framework model, mountain, policies, strategies

1. Introduction

If in the long term for the European Union things seem to be in order, with a number of guidelines to be achieved for rural development in general by 2030, for the development of the mountain area there are at least four specific targets to be considered, namely: (1) - Integrated strategies using collaborative and participatory approaches; (2) - Sustainable management of natural resources; (3) - Widespread digital literacy and opportunities to acquire more advanced skills; (4) - Enterprising, innovative and skilled people who together create technological, environmental and social progress [41, 42].

Adapting to the situation for the Romanian mountains we have in mind several considerations that make it appropriate for the future to achieve an integrated development framework. Thus, in general we observe that science is in a continuous search for concepts, principles and new directions of action, especially for mountain areas because the mountain reality is extremely complex. It is

becoming increasingly evident that mountain areas are becoming fragile both as a set of millennial chains on life cycles and in the relationship between mountain people and nature, underpinned by historical deficits in technologies, investments, skills, energy and raw material consumption and costs [1, 2, 6, 10, 15, 25]. We note that traditional agro-silvo-pastoral activities are less and less present in our mountains, especially under climate change [3, 7, 40].

To solve the problems, we must start from the diagnosis of the challenges for the mountain area [16, 19, 35, 36]: - in this area it must be decided whether this area can enter as a partner, together with upland agriculture, in solving the FAO objectives of feeding the planet; - then it must be decided whether the upland area remains with the same poorly productive technologies or introduces innovation and improvement on a large scale; - it must also be decided whether upland areas will be able to integrate productivity goals into policies to provide compensatory payments for the significantly higher costs of production; - last but not least, it must be decided

whether an intensive skills acquisition policy for high productivity farming practices (the whole educational chain: secondary, high school, vocational, higher education).

In view of all this, the present study attempts to find solutions to the complicated problems of the mountain area, through a few specific objectives necessary to develop an integrated mountain development model. We refer to the highlighting of some reference principles, then to the specific characteristics for mountain policies and strategies, as well as to the analysis of the necessary elements of the integration process regarding the evolution and development of Romanian mountain areas.

2. Working Method

The study is conceptually based on Theory of Bioharmonism [20, 21], as well as a series of comparative, economic, social and informational statistical analyses. Elements of multi-criteria analysis are addressed and a managerial and legal diagnosis with emphasis on the socio-economic aspects of the components of the integrated mountain system is used. Principles, techniques and regulations specific to sustainable development are considered in relation to the development of mountain areas on multiple levels (local, national, regional, continental, global).

3. Results and discussions

For the elaboration of the variant of a strategy for the development of mountain areas, based on the principles of techno-economic balances, smart growth and societal bio-harmony, it is necessary to take into account mountain diversity, sustainable development, economic evolution and policy decisions of mountain areas, and not only [9,13,14,23,28,31].

The natural geographical, climatic and pedological diversity of the mountains and, implicitly, biological diversity through genetic variability, are undeniable elements of reality and societal development. For these reasons, economic and social vision, engineering and management, science and technology, in addition to the principles of mountain science, will highlight the need for yield, optimization and maximization of evolution and sustainable development that will take into account the altitude gradient and the specificity of each mountain area.

Unfortunately, political decisions at the level of Romanian mountain areas and related public policies, in too many respects, do NOT converge with science and knowledge, and the dilettantism and ignorance of the present are counterproductive to the future requirements of the mountain area (see deserted localities, low investment, unused resources, poor infrastructure, etc.).

3.1. Mountain Policies and Strategies

A first step towards a strategic solution to the mountain's difficult problems is to consider the Mountain Convergence Principle (MCP), which shows that the mountain can become an entity in its own right when the convergence of resources with technology and management will lead to emergence and sustainability on mountain massif profiles, becoming de facto balanced, bio-harmonized, self-sustaining and independent areas of refuge and social resilience.

The application of the principle will lead to finding the complementary elements necessary for the elaboration of the necessary and preliminary DOCUMENTS for the short- and medium-term mountain policy, i.e. the elaboration of Territorial Integrated Mountain Programs (TIMP), as well as the realization of the Rural Mountain and Mountain Product Code (RMMPC). Basically, we are talking about a certain managerial conduct [17,18,29,38,39,43,44].

The established legal system is implemented by the main element in mountain development represented by HUMAN RESOURCE, i.e. the people living in the mountains, those who work and are adapted to this fragile and difficult area. From this perspective, mountain programs are needed to identify high-profile "attractors" in order to maintain and perpetuate the population of the mountain area demographically, but also for those willing to settle in this area. We consider the idea of remote working in mountain areas, supported by the necessary infrastructure, to be a forward-looking aspect, which can make "remote mountain work" possible and in good conditions.

As a result, a series of specific strategic guidelines can be issued, for example on the main themes of general mountain science and specific guidelines on food and tourism [4,5,8,12,22,24,26,34,37].

Other activities considered as "attractors" for human resources are the fields of agri-tourism,

with emphasis on gastronomy and mountain tourism, which have a real potential for the Romanian Carpathians, i.e. for the profile of high-quality food and tourism with great health potential.

The application of specific Programs and Projects, as well as the principles of mountain science (such as mountain convergence), scientific solutions and recommended technologies, makes it possible to analyze and apply the "Farm to Fork Strategy" for the Carpathian Mountains in a coherent way.

As points of reference, we are talking about the "mountain product" found on the "farm to fork" axis, i.e. high-quality mountain agro-zootechnical foods and the resulting culinary preparations, which make possible the solid genesis of Romanian mountain gastronomy. These aspects are the very strategic lines of general mountain gastronomy and, implicitly, of the evolution of mountain gastronomy (Table 1).

Table 1. Recommendations in the mountain gastronomy development strategy
In the conceptual direction of the new cuisine (*la Nouvelle Cuisine*)

Gastronomic models applicable in mountain areas	CULINARY TECHNOLOGICAL TYPOLOGIES	OBS. On the development of mountain gastronomy
CUISINE OF EXCELLENCE	<i>Deep Innovation Technique</i> (complementary assimilation of various types of modern cuisines - nutritious, sensory and generating health - in order to achieve exceptional culinary experiences based on new food attributes).	Is a strategic direction to follow in mountain gastronomy of gastronomy: <i>- mountain food should not be just a consumer item, but a unique personal experience!</i>
	♦ Creative cuisine (molecular gastronomy; culinary constructivism; abstract cuisine; modern culinology etc.)	
	♦ <i>Health generating cuisine</i> (<i>preventive cuisine, principles of validated traditionalism, trophology, etc.</i>)	
FUSION (the combination of gastronomic cultures)	<i>Mixing / blending technique</i> (unexpected ingredients and styles practiced around the globe)	NOT recommended (is lost originality)
	♦ Local fusion cuisine (between provinces of a state)	
	♦ Regional fusion cuisine (between countries of continents)	
	♦ Intercontinental fusion cuisine (combinations of cultures from different continents)	
FAST-FOOD / SLOW-FOOD	<i>Simplified cooking technique</i> (fast food, limited number of products NOT requiring preparation laborious preparation, with on-the-spot or take-away)	NOT recommended (is lost high quality)
CUSTOMISED KITCHEN	<i>Kitchen technique - laboratory</i> (Innovative technologies based on principles of excellence and tradition)	IS a strategic direction to follow in gastronomy of the future
	♦ Innovative technologies based on scientific principles and artificiality (biocellular food, synthetic food, automated and/or robotic cooking machines)	NOT recommended (is lost manufacturing quality)

The next step, useful for mountain agro-rural development, is linked to the valorisation of mountain products of local communities through tourism in mountain areas with the valorisation

of landscape and genetic resources of mountain areas (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Basic structural components of mountain tourism, part of tourism responsible for the agro-sylvo-pastoral landscape, protected areas and intangible heritage of the Romanian

3.2. Elements for developing the framework model for integrated mountain development

Addressing these issues opens a window of opportunity for the principled analysis needed to create an integrated mountain development model. The multitude of factors relating to

sustainable development, both tangible and intangible [11,27,30,32,33,45], are taken into account. At this stage, it is necessary to select, group and develop the key strategic directions (fig.2).

Fig. 2. Benchmark components on the strategic directions of bioharmonised development of the Romanian mountain area

• ***Strategic directions and risk factors of mountain policies***

As mountain policy is a complex issue that requires a special approach, we consider it useful to specify some aspects that are disruptive factors that must be taken into account for a correct solution through mountain public policies

Thus, in order to achieve coherence in decision making, we mention that Romanian mountain policies, being directly linked to global mountain development strategies, will have to take into account the three types of problems common in many mountains of the planet, i.e. those that limit the room for manoeuvre in defining a mountain policy to be economically efficient and with real systemic effectiveness. We

refer briefly to the following factors : (a) The place given to mountainology in state accumulation, employment policy and balance of payments equilibrium, as well as in demographic policy; (b) The rate of growth of the number of mountain area dependents; (c) The coalition of social forces supporting the incumbent regimes and influencing the way the state proceeds in social arbitration (see the conflicting interests between the components of the mountain area system, marketing manipulations and false information in the standardisation and labelling of the mountain product).

The integration of the presented strategic directions can generate the idea of an integrated mountain development framework model (fig.3).

Fig. 3. Convergence of policies and strategies in the dynamics of developing the framework model for the evolution and development of the Romanian mountain area

It can be seen how the policies and strategies characteristic of the high and medium altitude area lead to the development of the integrated mountain development framework model based on conceptual convergence, polyvalence, application of specific principles, all strengthening the structure and functionality of the systemic model.

Beyond the correlations between the groups of elements mentioned above, a dynamic characterised by conceptual convergence can be observed, which aims at a good quality of mountain life by realising within the imagined model a theoretical reinterpretation supported by the process of conceptual synergy related to mountain issues:

- to analyse the dynamics of the theme in relation to public policies;
- to analyse the range of endorsements and techniques to the tough demands of the mountain;
- to identify the main milestones by combining approaches of academic perspectives with practical experience (convergence of science and technology with mountain policy).

- to avoid old practices so that new projects succeed in changing behavioural patterns, and that attempts are NOT just activities unusual eco-engineering activities, but rather a shift to a different conceptual level of systemic integration and bioharmonisation.

In this sense, in order to support the harmonization of **mountain bioariums**, the model aims to highlight the idea that the problems of analysis and design of mountain development, in addition to production issues, are equally important institutional considerations of distribution and equitable access to resources (an example is the pressing topicality of the regionalization of Romania), but also of interdisciplinarity, legislation and versatility of activity in a fragile area. (NB- **mountain bioariums** = the area of land that quantifies and values living organisms, i.e. the genetic resources needed mainly for food but also for mountain tourism). The polyvalence of the framework model for the development of mountain areas is based on: - balance in resources; - bioharmonisation of processes; - sustainability of mountain development. Three aspects of convergence can be defined in this relationship,

namely: (a) the "engineering" elements, (b) the "management" elements and (c) the "culture and spirituality" elements in mountain areas. Within

these groups the model foresees the following elements to be addressed (Table 2).

Table 2. *The versatility of the integrated development framework model of mountain areas and the main lines of action*

Crt.no.	COURSES OF ACTION	SPECIFY
1.	ENGINEERING aspects	- Infrastructure in mountain areas
		- integrated and adapted economic activity
		- mountain ecology and climatology
2.	Aspects of MANAGEMENT	- development of public policies to harmonise mountain identity with the dynamics of European integration
		- administrative organisation
		- financial taxonomy (especially on agriculture)
3.	Aspects of CULTURE and SPIRITUALITY	- elements of mountain anthropology
		- mountain folklore (customs, traditions, artistic creations)
		- elements of mountain education and ecclesiastical culture

By analysing this polyvalence, as a premise for the elaboration of a model as a reference for mountain development, one can actually realise

the structural basis of the mountain system under analysis (fig.4).

Fig. 4. *Convergent structure of the mountain development model*

Although it is a structure of development model syntheses, however, it is possible to see relatively

well the connections between elements having as a common point of analysis the Mountain

Convergence Principle. This makes it possible to interpret the 'framework model' in a processual

way, especially in the context of adaptation to climate change (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Functioning based on multiple integration with emergent effect (integroneic dynamics) of processes specific to the mountain development model

Establishing the systemic benchmarks for the structure and functioning of the integrated mountain development model is the theoretical step needed to move on to the strategic implementation of this model. Sectoral and specific objectives can be set in a UNIFIED and CONSISTENT manner, which will be expressed through programs and projects covering all aspects of development in the mountain area and, above all, by finding working methodologies and ways of involving the existing players in this geographical area.

The proposed objectives of course involve both value issues and conflicts of interest, which makes it necessary for the public (individuals, mountain residents) to participate in the debate. It is therefore more than appropriate to involve all stakeholders (which has proved difficult over the years in our country), including the public sector, professional organizations and civil society, in order to establish, on the basis of the framework model, the options for a development strategy for upland areas and the impact of the various measures taken in individual mountain ranges and even at bioariums level.

Therefore, a far-reaching reform based on public policies, coherently framed in the FRAMEWORK MODEL with its new perspective on the problems and possible solutions with potential applicability for the protection of fragile areas such as mountain areas, is needed. And what is important to note is that all of this is funded, i.e. there is a real chance that knowing what needs to be done will lead to practical implementation in the coming decades.

We're talking about about €16 billion of European funds allocated for the development of agriculture and rural areas in Romania for the period 2023-2027 (of course including the one third of mountain areas in the total national area), through Romania's National Strategic Plan for Agriculture.

4. Conclusions

The real potential for the Romanian Carpathians is the profile of high-quality food and tourism with a high health generating potential, which indicates "mountain attractor" type activities such as: mountain agro-zootechnics, tourism and

gastronomy on mountain massif profiles, as well as remote mountain work.

Romanian mountain policies, being directly linked to global mountain development strategies, will have to consider the problems that limit the room for maneuver in defining an economically efficient mountain policy with real systemic effectiveness, namely: the place given to the "mountain" in state accumulation, employment policy, balance of payments and demographic policy; the rate of growth of the number of people dependent on the mountain area; the identification of the coalition of social forces that support the regimes in office and that influence the way the state proceeds in social arbitration.

Policies and strategies characteristic of mountain areas lead to the development of the systemic model as a new perspective of integrated mountain development based on conceptual convergence, the polyvalence of mountain areas, the application of specific principles, all of which reinforce the structure and functionality of the framework model.

The structure and functioning of the integrated mountain development model is the theoretical step needed to move on to the strategies for actually implementing this model in practice, by setting sectoral objectives and specific objectives, expressed through programs and projects covering all aspects of development in the mountain area and, above all, finding ways of involving the actors living in this geographical area.

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